

Development and application of stability indicating RP-HPLC method for the determination of mecobalamin in pharmaceutical formulations

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Abstract : The present work describes a simple and fast stability indicating reversed phase high performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for the quantitative determination of mecobalamin in pure and pharmaceutical tablet formulations. The chromatographic separation was achieved by the optimized mobile phase consisting of methanol and water (90 : 10) at pH 4.0 on shimpack column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5.0 μm particle size). The flow rate was kept at 1.0 ml/min, and the injection volume was 20 μL. The eluted compounds were monitored at 265 nm using a UV detector. The developed method separates mecobalamin and its degradation products within a run time of 5 min. The drug shows degradation under acidic, basic, photo oxidative and neutral conditions. Linearity of the method was found to be 5–75 μg/ml with correlation co-efficient of 0.9998. The proposed method was validated according to ICH guidelines with respect to accuracy, precision, linearity, specificity, robustness, limits of detection and quantification.

Keywords : Mecobalamin, stability indicating, RP-HPLC, chromatography, pharmaceutical formulations, ICH guidelines.

Introduction

Mecobalamin (Co α -[α -(5,6-Dimethylbenz-1*H*-imidazolyl)]-Co β -methylcobamide) occurs as dark red crystals or crystalline powder. Its chemical formula is [C₆₃H₉₁CoN₁₃O₁₄P] with molecular weight of 1344.38¹. Methylcobalamin (mecobalamin, MeCbl, or MeB12) is a cobalamin used in the treatment of peripheral neuropathy, diabetic neuropathy, and as a preliminary treatment for amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. It is a form of vitamin B12 and differs from cyanocobalamin in which the cyanide is replaced by a methyl group². Methylcobalamin features an octahedral cobalt(III) centre. Methylcobalamin can be obtained as bright red crystals³. Some important uses of mecobalamin include an improvement in reflexes, vibration sense, lower motor neuron weakness, and sensitivity to pain was also observed⁴. Cell culture and *in vivo* experimental results indicated methylcobalamin inhibited the proliferation of malignant cells⁵. Under experimental conditions, methylcobalamin inhibited HIV-1 infection of normal human blood monocytes and lymphocytes⁶.

A detailed literature survey for mecobalamin revealed

that few analytical methods are available using HPTCL⁷, RP-HPLC^{8–11}, HPLC-MS¹² in the presence of other vitamins and drugs. Some spectrophotometric methods using multivariate calibration techniques¹³. Partial least-squares method¹⁴, Vierodt's method¹⁵ and simple UV method have been reported. Literature review shows that no stability indicating analytical method for mecobalamin in tablets formulations has been reported by RP-HPLC. Only determination of mecobalamin by HPLC has been reported in the presence of other vitamins simultaneously.

The current research work reports for the first time a stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for the determination of mecobalamin in bulk drug and tablet dosage forms, which has a potential application to determine mecobalamin in stability samples. Also the cost of the analysis using LC-MS and HPTLC is very high and tedious compared to RP-HPLC in routine quality control analysis. However, the available spectrophotometric methods are not selective and stability indicating in their results. Hence, we focused on developing a selective, fast, cost-effective and stability-indicating method using this advance technique (RP-HPLC) for the quantitative determination of

mecobalamin in solid pharmaceutical dosage forms.

Hence a reproducible stability-indicating RP-HPLC method was developed which is less time consuming and more selective as compared to the reported methods, which takes only about 5 min for a single run. Thereafter, this method was successfully validated according to the ICH guideline¹⁷. Raw material of mecobalamin is only official in Japan Pharmacopeia. While its pharmaceutical formulation is not official in any Asian or European Pharmacopeia.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of mecobalamin.

Experimental

Materials and reagents :

Reference standard of mecobalamin (99.6%) and Neuromax tablets were procured as gift samples from BioFine Pharmaceutical, Multan, Pakistan. HPLC grade methanol was obtained from Tedia (USA). Hydrochloric acid was obtained from Merck Ltd.

Instrumentation :

Photo stability studies were carried out in a photostability chamber (HMG, India). Thermal stability studies were performed in a dry air oven (Mettler, Germany). HPLC system consisted of an LC-20 AT Shimadzu pump, SPD-20 Shimadzu UV visible detector, both connected by CBM-20 communication Bus Module Shimadzu to Intel Pentium IV machine with Shimadzu LC Solution Version 1.22 SP1 and Rheodyne manual injector fitted with a 20 μ L loop were used. The mobile phase was

sonicated by ultrasonic bath LC 30H Elma (Germany) and filtered through 0.45 μ m Millipore membrane filter, calibrated Pyrex glassware was used for the solution and mobile phase preparation. pH of the buffer solutions was monitored by Milwaukee (Singapore) pH meter.

Chromatographic conditions :

A mixture of methanol and water (90 : 10) at pH 4.00 was found to be the most suitable mobile phase for ideal separation of mecobalamin. The solvent mixture was filtered through a 0.45 μ m membrane filter and sonicated before use. It was pumped through the column at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. The column was maintained at ambient temperature. The column was equilibrated by pumping the mobile phase through the column for at least 30 min prior to the injection of the drug solution. The run time was set at 5 min. Under these optimized chromatographic conditions, the retention time obtained for the drug was 2.6 min. A typical chromatogram showing the separation of the drug is given in Fig. 2. The 20 μ L volume of sample was injected per run and effluents were detected using UV detector at 265 nm.

Preparation of mobile phase and diluents :

900 ml of the methanol was mixed with 100 ml of water and its pH was adjusted to 4.00 with 0.1 N HCl aqueous solution. The solution was degassed in an ultrasonic water bath for 5 min and filtered through 0.45 μ m filter under vacuum. Mobile phase was used as diluent.

Standard solution preparation :

Accurately weighed and transferred 50 mg of mecobalamin reference standard into 100 ml volumetric flasks, added about 70 ml of diluent and sonicated to dissolve it completely and made the volume up to the mark with the same solvent. 5 ml of the above stock solution was added to a 100 ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent. Mixed well and filtered through 0.45 μ m filter.

Preparation of stock solution :

Accurately weighed and transferred 50 mg of mecobalamin API sample into a 100 ml volumetric flask, added about 70 ml of diluent and sonicated to dissolve it completely and made the volume up to the mark with the same solvent. This is our stock solution. Then from this stock solution prepared the concentrations 10, 20, 30, 40

Fig. 2. Chromatogram of no stress treatment sample.

and 50 µg/ml by taking 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5 ml of stock solution in 25 ml of volumetric flask diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Construction of calibration curve :

Injected different concentrations into the chromatographic system and measured the peak area. Plotted a graph of peak area versus concentration. The regression equation of this curve was computed and used to determine the amount of mecobalamin in tablet dosage forms.

Procedure for determination of mecobalamin in tablet dosage forms :

Three commercial brands of tablets were chosen for testing the application of the proposed method to determine mecobalamin in commercial tablet dosage forms. Twenty tablets were weighed and powdered. An accurately weighed portion of this powder equivalent to 50 mg of mecobalamin was transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in 70 ml diluent. The contents of the flask were sonicated for 5 min, the flask was shaken continuously for 1 min to ensure complete solubility of the drug. The volume was made up with the diluent and the solution was filtered through a 0.45 µm membrane filter. Then took 5 ml from this solution and diluted to 100 ml with same solvent. This solution containing 25 µg/ml of mecobalamin was injected into the column three times. The average peak area of the drug was computed from the chromatograms and the amount of the drug present in the tablet dosage form was calculated by using the regression equation obtained for the pure drug.

Forced degradation studies :

In order to ensure that the analytical method was stability indicating, stress studies were performed.

Acid degradation studies :

1 ml of 0.1 N hydrochloric acid was added to 99 ml of drug solution to get the final concentration of 10 µg/ml of drug. This solution was allowed to stand for 24 h.

Alkali degradation studies :

1 ml of 0.1 N sodium hydroxide was added to 99 ml of drug solution to get the final concentration of 10 µg/ml of drug. This solution was allowed to stand for 24 h.

Photochemical degradation :

The photochemical stability of the drug was studied by exposing the stock solution (100 mg/ml) to direct sunlight for 5 min on a wooden plank and kept on terrace. The solutions were exposed to sunlight during the day time. The photochemical stability of the drug was also performed by keeping the stock solution (100 mg/ml) in the stability chamber for 12 h.

Thermal degradation :

The degradation behavior of drug in thermal condition was studied by placing the 50 mg dry powder of pure drug at 80 °C for 12 h. Then this powder was used for further analysis.

Peroxide degradation :

About 1 mL of 30% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) was added to 30 ml of drug solution and sonicated for 5 min

under heated at 60 °C for 12 h. This solution was allowed to stand for 24 h. Then the contents were diluted to volume of 100 ml with diluents to get the final concentration of 10 µg/ml of drug. Mix well and filter through 0.45 µm filter.

Neutral hydrolysis degradation :

Ten ml of mecobalamin standard working solution was heated with 10 ml water in a temperature controlled water bath maintained at 70 °C for 12 h.

Results and discussion

Method development :

The main criteria for development of successful RP-HPLC method for determination of mecobalamin in tablets were : the method should be able to determine assay of drug in single run and should be accurate, reproducible, robust, stability indicating, free of interference and can be easily used for routine analysis in quality control laboratory. To develop a suitable LC method for the analysis of mecobalamin in pure and its dosage form, different mobile phases were tried. The criteria employed for selecting the mobile phase for the analyses of the drug was its cost, time required for the analysis and better separation of drug and its impurities. The optimum mobile phase containing methanol and water 90 : 10 (v/v) (pH 4.0 ± 0.02, adjusted with 0.1 N HCl) was selected because it could resolve the peaks of mecobalamin at retention time of 2.6 min. Quantification was achieved with UV detection at 265 nm on the basis of peak area at 1.0 ml/min flow rate.

Validation of the proposed method :

The specificity, linearity, precision, accuracy, limit of detection, limit of quantification and robustness were studied systematically to validate the proposed analytical method for the determination of mecobalamin. Solution containing 25 µg/ml of mecobalamin was subjected to the proposed RP-HPLC analysis to check intra-day and inter-day variation of the method and the results are presented in Table 2.

Linearity and range :

Five different concentrations (10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 µg/ml) of drug solution were prepared for linearity studies. A typical HPLC chromatogram obtained during de-

termination of mecobalamin is shown in Fig. 2. The calibration curve obtained by plotting peak area against concentration showed linear relationship over a concentration range of 5–75 µg/ml. The regression equation of the linearity plot of concentration of mecobalamin its peak area was found to be $y = 197582x - 186742$ ($R^2 = 0.9998$), where x is the concentration (µg/ml) of mecobalamin and y is the corresponding peak area (Fig. 3). Regression characteristics of the proposed RP-HPLC method are given in Table 1.

Fig. 3. Calibration curve.

Table 1. Regression characteristics and validation parameters for the analysis of mecobalamin

Parameters	Values
System suitability :	
Retention time (min)	2.6
Theoretical plates count	7458
Tailing factor	1.21
Linearity range (µg/ml)	5–75
Limit of detection (µg/ml)	0.647
Limit of quantification (µg/ml)	1.96
Regression analysis :	
Slope	197582
Intercept	186742
Correlation coefficient	0.9999

Precision :

Precision was studied to find out intra- and inter-day variations in the proposed method of mecobalamin at concentration of 25 µg/ml on the same day and three different days respectively. The percentage Relative Standard Deviation was calculated for intra- and inter-day precision and found to be less than 2%. The results of precision are presented in the Table 2.

Table 2. Precision of the proposed method

Concentration of mecobalamin (25 µg/ml)	Peak area	
	Inter-day	Intra-day
Injection-1	393967	401673
Injection-2	393915	400678
Injection-3	393087	401467
Injection-4	394053	401456
Injection-5	394298	401672
Average	328221	401389
Standard Deviation	459	411
% RSD	0.12	0.10

Recovery study :

The accuracy of the proposed method was determined by calculating recovery of mecobalamin 20%, 50% and 100% was added to a pre-quantified sample solution. The recovery studies were carried out three times over the specified concentration range and the percentage recovery of mecobalamin was found to be in the range of 99.86–99.88% and the results are presented in Table 3.

Robustness :

Robustness of the method was studied by changing the λ_{max} from 263 to 267 and flow rate from 0.8 ml to 1.2 ml. The results showed that the retention time and peak area of mecobalamin remained almost unchanged and no significant degradation was observed (Table 4).

Limit of Detection (LOD) :

Limit of Detection can be calculated using the following equation according to ICH guidelines : $LOD = 3.3$

$\times s/Slope$ where s is the standard deviation of peak area of the drug. The results are shown in Table 1.

Limit of Quantification (LOQ) :

Limit of Quantification can be calculated using the following equation according to ICH guidelines : $LOQ = 10 \times s/Slope$ where s is the standard deviation of peak area of the drug. The results are shown in Table 1.

Stability indicating property :

The photolysis of aqueous methylcobalamin (mecobalamin) is well known to lead to the homolysis of the cobalt-carbon sigma bond in the primary photochemical step¹⁸.

In the absence of oxygen an efficient regeneration of methylcobalamin takes place, while in the presence of oxygen an irreversible product formation occurs¹⁹.

The chromatogram of no stress treatment sample (as control) showed no additional peak (Fig. 2). The retention time of standard and sample were 3.626 min. The chromatogram of acid degraded sample showed no additional peaks (Fig. 4). The chromatogram of alkali degraded sample showed no additional peaks (Fig. 5). The chromatogram of thermal degraded sample showed no additional peaks (Fig. 6). The chromatogram of photo degraded sample showed one major additional peak at re-

Table 3. Recovery studies ($n = 3$)

Label claim (mg/tab)	Amount added (mg)	Total amount (mg)	Amount recovered (mg) \pm RSD (%)	% Recovery
1000	200	1200	1198.45 \pm 0.89	99.87
1000	500	1500	1497.98 \pm 0.78	99.86
1000	1000	2000	1997.67 \pm 0.57	99.88

Table 4. Robustness study

	Flow rate (ml)				Wavelength (nm)			
	0.8 ml		1.2 ml		263		267	
	Peak area	Tailing factor	Peak area	Tailing factor	Peak area	Tailing factor	Peak area	Tailing factor
	978852	0.995	972686	0.914	975685	1.2	976648	1.1
	978814	0.985	974585	0.982	982586	1.1	978545	1.1
	978845	0.979	978642	0.941	974885	1.2	978512	0.998
Mean	978837		975304.3		977718.7		977901.7	
SD	20		3042		4234		1086	

Fig. 4. Chromatogram of acid degraded sample.

Fig. 5. Chromatogram of alkali degraded sample.

Fig. 6. Chromatogram of thermal degraded sample.

tention time of 2.342 min and one minor peak at 3.016 min in addition to the major peak of the mecobalamin at 2.640 (Fig. 7). It means mecobalamin show remarkable degradation i.e. 30.56% in direct light exposed condi-

tions. However mecobalamin itself is light sensitive compound. Similarly the chromatogram of peroxide degradation sample show one minor peak at 1.80 min and major peak 2.630 min (Fig. 8). Some sort degradation also ob-

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served under these conditions that is almost 9.8%. While in neutral hydrolysis condition the sample does not show any additional peak that confirms no degradation (Fig.

9). The relevant peak areas of the various treated samples, their peak area, % degradation and assay percentage are shown in Table 5.

Fig. 7. Chromatogram of photo degraded sample.

Fig. 8. Chromatogram of peroxide degraded sample.

Fig. 9. Chromatogram of neutral hydrolysis degraded sample.

Fig. 10. Chromatogram of dosage forms (mecobalamin).

Table 5. Stress study of mecobalamin

Sr. no.	Condition	Time (h)	Retention time	Peak area	% Assay	% Degradation
1.	No stress treatment	0	2.656	391117	99.3	0.72
2.	Alkali	24	2.716	392544	99.6	0.36
3.	Acid	24	2.639	391376	99.3	0.66
4.	Light	12	2.640	273406	69.4	30.56
5.	Thermal	12	2.724	368231	93.5	6.53
6.	Oxidative	12	2.630	352689	90.2	9.8
7.	Neutral	12	2.741	391397	99.9	0.1

Solution stability and mobile phase stability :

To study the stability of sample solution and mobile phase we stored them at ambient temperature for 24 h. Mecobalamin sample solution was re-analyzed after 12 and 24 h by using the same mobile phase. The assay result was calculated and compared with fresh sample. Sample solution did not show any considerable change in assay value when stored at ambient temperature up to 24 h, which are presented in Table 6. The results from solution stability experiments confirmed that sample solution and mobile phase was stable for up to 24 h during assay determination.

Table 6. Solution and mobile phase stability results

	Initial	After 12 h	After 24 h
% Assay	100.52	99.78	99.62
	99.47	99.12	99.51

Conclusion

A stability indicating RP-HPLC method has been developed and validated for the purity determination of mecobalamin. The method developed for mecobalamin was found to be simple, precise, sensitive, rapid, robust and economical. The behavior of mecobalamin under various stress conditions was studied. Moreover the proposed method allows separation of studies drug from its alkaline, acid, light, thermal, oxidative and neutral degradation products within a very short time. The analytical conditions developed with good resolution within a short analysis time. Thus it can be conveniently applied for the testing of batch release and stability studies in quality control laboratories.

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